

Polymer Nanocomposite Triboelectric Nanogenerators for Antimicrobial and Electrical Stimulation Platforms

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Research Areas

- 2D layered nanofillers
graphene, clay

- Surface functionalization

Polymer Nanocomposites

Nano-Thin Film Coatings

Materials Characterization

- Multifunctional thin film coating applications

- Layer-by-layer (LbL) self-assembly

- Microimaging (TEM, SEM, AFM)

- (b) - Mechanical

- Thermal (TGA, DSC)
- X-ray (SAXS, XRD)
- Thin film (ellipsometry, UV-vis, FT-IR, QCM)

Layer-by-Layer (LbL) Assembly

- Electrostatic self-assembly

- Ambient processing
- Nanoscale control
- Tunable properties

[1] G. Decher, J. B. Schlenoff, *Multilayer Thin Films: Sequential Assembly of Nanocomposite Materials*, Wiley-VCH, 2012

[2] Grunlan Research Group, Texas A&M University

Layer-by-Layer Advantage: DIVERSITY

- LbL can involve nearly any type of macromolecule
 - . Nanoparticles, QDs
 - . Nanotubes, nanowires
 - . Nanoplatelets (e.g., clay, graphene)
 - . Dyes, dendrimers
 - . DNA, proteins, viruses, etc...

*G. Decher, *Science* **1997**, 277, 1232.

Sensor Applications

IEEE Sens. J. **9**, 1308 (2007)

Energy Applications

Adv. Mater. **23**, 1514 (2011)

Antimicrobial Applications

Nano Lett. **8**, 1896 (2008)

Pharmaceutical Applications

ACS Nano **4**, 3725 (2010)

Introduction to LbL Assembly

Energy Harvesting

Mechanical Energy: one of the most desirable sources

→ no constraint of time and location

Triboelectric Nanogenerators

- **Triboelectricity = Triboelectrification + Electrostatic Induction**

Four fundamental working modes of the TENGs

(Long L et al. *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2015, 8, 2250-2282)

TENG Applications

Applications of the triboelectric signals

Diversity of material

Positive ↑	Air	Nitrile	Negative ↓
	Human skin	Rubber	
	Fur	Nickel, copper	
	PLA	Silver	
	Glass	Gold	
	Human hair	PC	
	Nylon	PET	
	Wool	Polyester	
	Silk	Polyethylene	
	Aluminum	Polypropylene	
	Paper	Polyimide	
	Cotton	PVC	
	Steel	PDMS	
	Wood	FEP	

[Nano Energy, 2020]

Simple mechanism

[Sensors, 2018]

Miniaturization

[Nat. Commun., 2015]

Flexibility

[Nano Energy, 2020]

Transparency

[IJPEM-GT, 2021]

Energy Harvester

Self-powered Sensor

Electrical Stimulator

[Adv. Energy Mater., 2018]

Energy harvester

&

Self-powered sensor

➔ Applications of triboelectric signal with the **unique advantages** as the **energy harvester** and **self-powered sensor**

[1] Skin-like Free-Standing TENGs

➤ Highly Stretchable, Designable, Patch-type Thin Film TENG

Triboelectric Performance of FS-TENGs

[2] Biopolymer Antimicrobial TENG

➤ Fabrication of eco-friendly and biodegradable patch-type TENG

(a) i) [PVA/GNP-PSS]₃ Electrode (GL)

ii) [CH/AL]_n Positive TM

iii) TENG

Biopolymer Antimicrobial TENG

➤ Objective: to Fabricate eco-friendly and biodegradable patch-type TENG

Skin-patch TENG sensor

[3] Biodegradable LbL Gelatin-TENG

➤ Self-Assembled Biodegradable Gelatin Thin Films

Worldwide production of Gelatin

Annually generates approximately 7.3 million tons of waste in the form of **fish skin, bones, and fins**. (major byproduct!)

LbL Gelatin-TENG Applications

[4] TENG-based Electrical Stimulation

➤ Antibacterial Electrical-Stimulation Platform with Sterilizing Particles

- ❖ Schematic of the fabrication process
- ❖ Chitosan as reducing agent
- ❖ UV-vis spectra (different Ag^+)

- ❖ Antibacterial agar plate diffusion results for the bacterial strains after 24h.

Antibacterial Performance

- ❖ Antibacterial performance after electrical stimulation
- ❖ Proposed mechanism for Antimicrobial

- ❖ Amounts of silver ions released

To Improve Parkinson's Disease Behavior

- ❖ Electrical stimulation is biosafe and does not affect with the growth of *C. elegans*.

- ❖ Improving Parkinson's-related symptoms by electrical stimulation

N2- wild type

BSR
 ■ N2 (off food)
 ■ N2 (on food)

CB112 - mutant w/ lack of dopamine production

■ CB112 (off food)
 ■ CB112 (on food)

[5] TENG-based Electrical Stimulation

➤ Advance to Antibacterial Electrical-Stimulation Platform

❖ Schematic of the Hydrogel Fabrication Process

❖ Synthesis Optimization

❖ Antibacterial Performance

Triboelectric Performance

❖ PVC/Chitosan/ZnO Hydrogel-based TENG

❖ Antibacterial Performance

Antibacterial Performance

❖ PVC/Chitosan/ZnO Hydrogel-based TENG

Triboelectric Performance

Material	Voltage	Type of bacteria	Concentration of bacterial	Time TENG working	Antibacterial performance	Reference
PPY/PCL film	5V	E. coli and S.aureus	1×10^5 CFU/mL	16 h	96%	(Tang et al., 2023)
MoS ₂ /GelMA hydrogel	48.80 V	E. coli	1×10^4 CFU/mL	30 min	100 %	(H. Yu et al., 2024)
PA-CHI-Ag electric fiber	31.3 V	E. coli and S.aureus	2.2×10^4 CFU/mL	18 h	99%	(Tian & Hua, 2021)
MLDH@Al film	8V	E. coli and S.aureus	1×10^5 CFU/mL	24 h	100%	(Du et al., 2021b)
PPy-GO thin film	-	S.aureus	0.5×10^8 CFU/mL	25 min	75%	(Jannesari et al., 2023)
GO-Al film	150-300V	E. coli and S.aureus	0.5×10^8 CFU/mL	25 min	95-98%	(Jannesari et al., 2024)
Minocycline-loaded hydrogel	5V	E. coli and S.aureus	1×10^5 CFU/mL	24 h	95%	(W. Wang et al., 2024)
Au-PP film	8 V	E. coli and S.aureus	1×10^7 CFU/mL	-	99%	(Yi et al., 2025)
PVA-CHI-ZnO hydrogel	~100V	E. coli and S.aureus	0.5×10^8 CFU/mL	5 min	100%	This study

Conclusions

- ✓ **Biocompatible Hydrogel and Thin Films** were fabricated and used as triboelectric materials.
- ✓ **Fabrication Process** was optimized and adapted to TENG.
- ✓ **Antibacterial Effect has been enhanced** by electrical stimulation from thin-film TENG platform.
- ✓ TENG-based electrical stimulation was used for **the first time to improve Parkinson's disease behavior.**

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